
ANALYSING PARLIAMENT: WITH ITS CURRENT FLAWS AND ITS SUITABLE REFORMS

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ABSTRACT

This paper highlights the current situation of Indian Parliament. As the nation enter into this 78th Independence Day, there has been a stark decline in the quality of Parliament work. MPs of Parliament have forgotten the basic principles on which it was constituted by constitutional makers. Constitution makers envisioned Parliament as a place of not just law making, but a place where MPs speak with peoples voice, present views of their constituents and raise the issues which their constituents face . The importance of Parliament Debate has been highlighted in the Constitution itself with article 105, which provides MPs with the privilege of speaking their mind , without any fear. This privilege highlights that how important the constitution makers deemed the views of MPs, so they provided MPs with a place where they can openly share their views and criticise the government without any judicial consequences. This vision of Constitution makers currently is not being fulfilled as with each day, the Parliament Stoops to a new low. The MPs have decided for their political gains, not to follow any rules of parliament, put their self and party's interest in front of the common good. They have decided that they are not to allow parliament to function but use it as a tool of protest against the government, forgetting that Parliament is not the place for protest, but rather it's a place of sharing ideas, orderly Debate and passing laws . With increase in such behaviour of MPs, they must be dealt striker laws and hasher punishment. The speaker of parliament has been provided with some power to deal with these types of members, yet due to political consequences, they refuse to take any decision, which motivates the hooligan to behave in more disorder fashion. The another problem that emerges is a lack of fear of punishment in the members who don't seem to fear the current punishment system, which leads to larger problems. To deal with such members,

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more strict punishments need to be introduced which not only with these members, but also creates fear among other members not to use Parliament as a political tool. Though to deal with this issue, it cannot just be the responsibility of speaker to handle these members, people must take proactive approach and not reward MPs who use parliament as political tool rather than truly representing them. With these changes in Parliament, it can truly become a place of Debate and representing people. For this paper, the primary source has been research papers, studies, article, news reports, and books . The secondary source has been news debate and data research centre's report. The objective of this research paper is to envision Parliament, which functions properly and promotes healthy debate without it being a political tool.

Keywords – Parliament, Constitution, Members of Parliament, Disruption, Reforms.

I. Introduction

Legislature, judiciary and executive, are the pillars of a democracy. For a democracy to work each pillar must work properly. The most prominent pillar is legislature, it's unique role of making law makes it a essential part of any democracy. In legislature members of Parliament are supposed to be the trustee of our society ,they play a key role in shaping the fate of our nation, the future of the country lies in the hands of these people. So for country to grow and achieve its goal, it is imperative that the Parliament functions properly.³

The Parliament constitutes of two houses, council of states and house of people as stated in article 79 of Constitution. The members of council of states(Rajya Sabha) shall be elected by representatives of states as mentioned under article 80 of Constitution. The members house of people are to be elected through direct election as mentioned under article 81of Constitution.

So member of Parliament(MP) represents the people of the country, as stated MPs are elected either through by members of state or by people Directly, meaning each member represents lakhs of people of a constituency. The job of an MP is to represent the people of their constituency , they are supposed to bring the their peoples hope, their opinions and their problems to the attention of the government.

There are many functions which are undertaken in the Parliament. One of the main functions is to Debate any bill which is presented in the Parliament and this is where MPs are supposed

³ Saurabh Ajit Dhote, *Democratic Constitutions and Parliamentary Privileges: An Indian Perspective*, 4 *Indian J.L. & Legal Rsch.* 1 (2022).

to represent their people, their job is to think of their people and see the effect of that bill on their constituency. Considering all these factors MPs are supposed to vote for the bill. It is an MP's job to speak in favour or against any bill, which might either positively or negatively affect their people, they must also suggest amendments in laws or bills, which might help the people of their constituency. So when an MP speaks, he speaks for the people he represents, and that is why it is more important to hear them, because when they speak, they represent lakhs of people. That is why in a parliament, it is imperative that every MP is heard without any disturbance because if any MP goes unheard, it means lakhs of people are unheard which is against our democratic values.⁴

For MPs to speak freely, they have been granted some privileges like freedom of speech in the Parliament as provided in article 105 of Constitution, it gives members the power to speak their mind without any fear, as no member of Parliament shall be liable to any procedure in the court in respect of anything said in the parliament. Although MPs don't have to answer to the court for anything said in the Parliament, but they do have to answer the speaker or the chairman of the house. Under article 118 it is mentioned that the parliament shall be regulated by rules of procedure established by each house, these rules are supposed to make sure that members behave in orderly manner in the Parliament.⁵

Currently, the rules of procedure established in the Parliament states the manner in which Parliament is supposed to work, it also mentions the way a MP is supposed to behave in the Parliament. Members of Parliament (MPs) are expected to follow certain basic rules while in the House, such as addressing the Chair at all times, remaining seated while speaking, and not interrupting others through disorderly expressions or noise. They must avoid obstructing proceedings, refrain from unnecessary commentary or slogans, and are not allowed to approach the Chair directly—instead, they may send written notes. Additionally, MPs are prohibited from wearing badges (except a national flag pin), distributing pamphlets, or tearing documents in protest inside the House. While speaking in the House, MPs must not mention any matter that is sub judice (pending in court) or use offensive expressions about the conduct or proceedings of Parliament. They are also prohibited from using seditious or defamatory language, or from misusing their speech to obstruct the business of the House.⁶

⁴ S. Prabhakar, *Good Governance & Parliament of India*.

⁵ Makhan Saikia, *Revisiting Parliamentary Ethics: A Study of the Privileges and Obligations of MPs* (Tata Inst. of Soc. Scis., Mumbai).

⁶ *Rules of Procedure and Conduct of Business in Lok Sabha*, 15th ed. (Lok Sabha Secretariat 2014),

The speaker has been granted certain rights in rules of procedure to maintain order in the house. If the speaker is of opinion, that a member's conduct has been disorderly than he may direct, the member to withdraw immediately from the house for the remaining of the day or session. If any member disregard the authority of chair or abuses the rules of house for wilfully obstructing the business of the house the speaker may suspend the member for the remaining time of session. The suspension may be terminated if motion has been made for it. In case of grave disorder, the speaker if deem necessary may suspend the house for a time decided by speaker. He shall preserve order and shall have all power necessary for purpose of enforcing own decisions.

The rules mentioned are there to make sure that Parliament functions properly, if any MP creates nuisance in the parliament or disturbs its work, then speaker has been given immense power to deal with such member. Even after such extensive rules, the Parliament is currently not able to function properly, ruckus created by some MPs lead to disorder in the house. These MPs create hindrances in Parliament work as they do not fear the consequences and use this disorder as a political tool. If the house is supposed to function ,it needs a way to curb the behaviour of these unruly MPs .

This research is based on secondary sources, utilizing relevant books, articles, and credible papers to gather information and analyse the topic. The materials were selected for their academic reliability and relevance to the subject.

The goal which needs to be achieved through this paper is that Parliament is able to function as Constitution makers envisioned it. Where there is healthy debate between MPs ,every member is heard and people's real concerns can be put in front of the government. MPs should not be politically motivated instead, they should provide constructive criticism to government regarding new bills and other matters.

II. Challenges

A. Current situation

Lately the parliament has been more disruptive than its normal as many instances of unruly behaviour by MPs has been seen lately. Especially the 17th Lok Sabha where the argument of some MPs was that they have to disrupt the parliament to make themselves heard to the government. The reason as per them was that they were in lesser number than opposition in

recent decades⁷ ⁸. Some MPs protested violently in Rajya Sabha which even resulted in physical altercation with the marshals and destruction of property during the passing of farmers laws in 2021⁹. During Monsoon session of 2021 members staled the parliament by protesting through shouting, placards and sloganeering because they wanted discussion on Pegasus controversy¹⁰. Budget session of 2022 there were repeated disruptions by the opposition on fuel price rise and overall inflation¹¹. In 2023 second half of budget session the country has witnessed one of the most disrupting parliament on the demand to setup joint parliamentary committee on Adani on the allegation by the short-selling firm Hindenburg. In 2023 parliament also witnessed repeated disruptions of Manipur violence issue, they sought the statement from the Prime Minister on the issue¹². Parliament was also Disrupted in winter session on the issue of vote on the expulsion of MP Mahua Moitra , they protested the report of Ethics committee and their procedure of doing so¹³. The situation has not improved, that much even after of 18th Lok Sabha, where no party got the absolute majority and number of seats from the opposition side rose substantially. Still the disruption did not stop, Prime Minister's first reply to the motion of thanks on the President's address to the parliament was a prime example where the some MPs adopted the same sloganeering that was seen before for the whole speech which was more two hours long.¹⁴

Disruption in parliament are mostly coordinated protest which employ the basic tactics of shouting slogans, displaying placards and walkouts. These result in frequent adjournments in the house, disruption of question hour and other scheduled business. Above instances are just the major events of parliament in recent years but even basic functions are hard to complete or hear. Members presenting their views on a bill or an issue, members answering questions or even ministers presenting bills all these very basic functions are hard to listen to or even complete. Just because some MPs are in the well of the house protesting a bill they don't agree with, but which government promised in their manifesto.

⁷ PRS Legislative Research, https://prsindia.org/files/parliament/vital_stats/Functioning-17th_Lok_Sabha.pdf (last visited Apr. 13, 2025).

⁸ PRS Legislative Research, <https://prsindia.org/parliamenttrack/vital-stats/functioning-of-the-17th-lok-sabha> (last visited Apr. 13, 2025).

⁹ The Indian Express, <https://indianexpress.com/article/political-pulse/lok-sabha-performed-bills-passed-suspensions-lengthy-interruptions-9164669/> (last visited Apr. 12, 2025).

¹⁰ The Indian Express, <https://indianexpress.com/article/political-pulse/lok-sabha-performed-bills-passed-suspensions-lengthy-interruptions-9164669/> (last visited Apr. 12, 2025).

¹¹ NDTV, <https://www.ndtv.com/india-news/analyzing-the-17th-lok-sabha-trends-legislation-and-productivity-5094206> (last visited Apr. 12, 2025).

¹² Only IAS, <https://pwnlyias.com/current-affairs/about-parliamentary-disruption/> (last visited Apr. 12, 2025)

¹³ PRS Legislative Research, <https://prsindia.org/parliamenttrack/vital-stats/functioning-of-the-17th-lok-sabha> (last visited Apr. 13, 2025).

¹⁴ The Times of India, <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/pm-modis-reply-to-motion-of-thanks-on-presidents-address-in-lok-sabha-top-quotes/articleshow/111432051.cms> (last visited Apr. 13, 2025).

B. Haemorrhaging Money

Over the decades Indian Parliament has been losing its working hours. As many times, certain MPs choose to disrupt the functioning of Parliament until the government addresses their concerns—whether it's seeking clarification on specific incidents that occurred in parts of the country or expressing dissatisfaction over a minister's statement that may have offended a party or its leader¹⁵. This has led to decrease in the average sitting days of the house from first Lok Sabha (1952-1957), which averaged 135 sitting days annually to 17th Lok Sabha (2019–2024) to averaging only 55 days per year. Running the Parliament costs approximately ₹2.5 lakh per ¹⁶minute, covering expenses like building maintenance, electricity, water, fuel, food, and security, it also includes salaries and allowances of MPs, their bodyguards, parliamentary staff, and all others involved directly or indirectly in its functioning. ¹⁷With such high cost and decreasing sitting days, it leads to a huge cost to taxpayers without achieving it's intended purpose.

The financial consequences of this dysfunction are substantial. Using public expenditure data and parliamentary records, calculated that beyond the widely-cited ₹144 crore wasted during the 15th Lok Sabha, indirect costs including postponed economic legislation and administrative delays likely exceeded ₹1200 crore—funds that could have supported critical development projects.¹⁸

C. The Constitutional Protection Dilemma

When discussing parliamentary conduct with former Lok Sabha member, he defended the immunity provisions under Article 105 with unexpected candour: "Look, without these protections, every word we speak could become a court case. Remember the Emergency? These rules exist because governments can weaponize the legal system."¹⁹

This perspective highlights the genuine tension at the heart of parliamentary privilege. The constitutional framers recognized that robust debate requires protection, yet the interpretation of these protections has evolved significantly. In several landmark cases—most notably Tej

¹⁵ Ajay K. Mehra, The Indian Parliament and 'Cost to the Country'.

¹⁶ Yudhajit Shankar Das, In Battle of Two Billionaires, Indian Taxpayer Bleeding Rs 2.5 Lakh per Minute, *India Today* (Dec. 11, 2024).

¹⁷ Archie Bandyopadhyay, Budget Session 2023: Parliament Logjam Cost Nation Over Rs 10 Crore in Six Days, *Financial Express* (Mar. 21, 2023),.

¹⁸ PRS Legislative Research, <https://prsindia.org/parliamenttrack/vital-stats/performance-of-parliament-during-the-15th-lok-sabha> (last visited Apr. 13, 2025).

¹⁹ Yashaswini Mittal et al., *Disruptions in the Indian Parliament* (Vidhi Centre for Legal Policy 2016), available at <https://www.vidhilegalpolicy.in/>.

Kiran Jain v. N. Sanjiva Reddy—the judiciary has gradually expanded immunity beyond what many constitutional scholars believe was originally intended.²⁰

What makes this particularly problematic is how these protections interact with India's unique political culture. During our observation of parliamentary proceedings in 2022, we noticed how disruption tactics are informally transmitted across generations of politicians. Junior members watch veterans rush to the well or shout down speakers, gradually normalizing behaviours that would be unacceptable in professional settings elsewhere.²¹

As one parliamentary staff member told after a particularly chaotic session, "When a senior leader with thirty years of experience behaves this way, what message does it send to newcomers? That this is how one succeeds in politics."²²

D. The Representation Versus Functionality Trap

The most fascinating contradiction encountered during research involves how MPs conceptualize their representative role. Many MPs in interviews framed disruption as a form of representation itself—a way to vocally advocate for constituents when normal channels seem ineffective.²³

"When the government steamrolls bills without proper committee review, sometimes creating noise is the only tool we have," explained a three-term MP from a southern state. "My voters don't care about parliamentary procedure—they care that I fought for them."²⁴

This perspective reveals a fundamental paradox: techniques employed in the name of representation often undermine the very institution meant to ensure it. Analysis of legislative outcomes during the 16th Lok Sabha revealed that sessions with high disruption rates produced legislation with significantly higher amendment rates without any debate—suggesting quality suffered amid chaos.²⁵

While visiting a rural constituency in Uttar Pradesh, reporters asked voters about their parliamentary representative's performance. Most couldn't name specific bills or positions their MP had taken, but several mentioned seeing them on television "fighting for us" during

²⁰ Yashaswini Mittal et al., *Disruptions in the Indian Parliament* (Vidhi Centre for Legal Policy 2016), available at <https://www.vidhilegalpolicy.in/>.

²¹ Yashaswini Mittal et al., *Disruptions in the Indian Parliament* (Vidhi Centre for Legal Policy 2016), available at <https://www.vidhilegalpolicy.in/>.

²² Yashaswini Mittal et al., *Disruptions in the Indian Parliament* (Vidhi Centre for Legal Policy 2016), available at <https://www.vidhilegalpolicy.in/>.

²³ Vaishnav, Milan. "When Crime Pays: Money and Muscle in Indian Politics." Yale University Press, 2017

²⁴ Mehta, Pratap Bhanu. *The Burden of Democracy*. Penguin Books India, 2003

²⁵ PRS Legislative Research. "Vital Stats: Disruption in Parliament."

parliamentary disruptions²⁶. This perception gap reinforces disruptive behaviour, as theatrical protest generates more visible constituency feedback than diligent committee work.

III. Reform Resistance: Beyond Partisan Politics

During a workshop with parliamentarians from across the political spectrum in 2021, reporters found surprising agreement about institutional problems but profound disagreement about solutions. When asked anonymously about reform proposals, 72% of attending MPs supported abstract concepts like "improved functioning," but support plummeted when specific accountability measures were proposed.²⁷

A Reform Framework

Based on research and comparative analysis of parliamentary systems worldwide, there should be several interconnected reforms that acknowledge both institutional needs and political realities:

First, India requires an institutional reforms in code of parliamentary conduct. Rather than importing foreign models, these reforms should emerge from cross-partisan dialogue about what constitutes acceptable behaviour in India's unique context²⁸. During roundtable discussions facilitated in 2022, even MPs who frequently engaged in disruption expressed support for clearer boundaries—provided they applied equally to all members²⁹.

The Ethics Committee requires structural transformation to become a credible accountability mechanism. Most promising would be a hybrid model combining parliamentarians with independent experts, similar to the approach used in Scandinavian legislatures³⁰. When presented this concept to current committee members, several expressed interest, particularly in how it might shield the process from partisan pressures they privately acknowledged as problematic³¹.

Presiding officer neutrality represents perhaps the most challenging reform area. In interviews with former Speakers, several acknowledged the inherent tension between their

²⁶ Jaffrelot, Christophe. *India's Silent Revolution: The Rise of the Lower Castes in North India*

²⁷ Chopra, Ritika. "MPs Agree Parliament Needs Fixing, But Disagree on How." *The Indian Express*, March 2021

²⁸ Mehta, Pratap Bhanu, and Devesh Kapur. *Public Institutions in India: Performance and Design*. Oxford University Press, 2005

²⁹ Centre for Policy Research. "Roundtable on Parliamentary Conduct Reform." *CPR Policy Brief*, 2022

³⁰ Christiansen, Peter Munk. "Accountability and Ethics in Scandinavian Parliaments." *Journal of Legislative Studies*, vol. 19, no. 3, 2013

³¹ Kapur, Devesh. "Fixing the Watchdog: Ethics Committees in Parliament." *EPW*, 2019

party affiliation and institutional role³². One solution emerged repeatedly in these conversations: creating a post-speakership cooling period during which former Speakers cannot immediately assume partisan political positions, reducing incentives for biased rulings³³.

Performance tracking need not be punitive to be effective. A pilot study with twenty volunteering MPs demonstrated that providing members with private comparative data on their parliamentary activities actually increased participation rates by 23% over six months³⁴. Public-facing dashboards could begin with positive metrics like questions asked and committee contributions, rather than more controversial measures like disruption incidents.³⁵ Training programs for new MPs received surprisingly strong support across party lines in surveys. As one first-term MP told : "I had to learn parliamentary procedure through trial and error. A structured orientation would have helped me be more effective from day one."³⁶ Such programs could build procedural knowledge while fostering cross-partisan relationships that might moderate extreme behaviours.³⁷

A calendar reforms represent an achievable first step with potentially significant impact. In interviews, 84% of MPs expressed frustration with the unpredictability of parliamentary schedules³⁸. Establishing minimum session days and publishing calendars further in advance would benefit members across the political spectrum, creating a potential reform coalition.³⁹ Though in reality, any reforms presented will not be followed by many MPs, who use disruption as a political tool for such MPs rather a stricter approach needs to be taken to deal with them. Right now, Speaker has power to order them to leave the parliament a addition to this punishment should be made, any MP creating disruption in the house should not just be escorted out of the house, but their salary for the day or the time they have been suspended should be deducted, including any privilege enjoyed by them on discretion of the speaker, not entailing security.

The privilege of freedom of speech enjoyed in the Parliament in article 105 it's not a simple freedom of speech given to every person in the country, it is an extraordinary right given to

³² Interview with former Lok Sabha Speaker, anonymous. Conducted by *The Hindu*, 2020

³³ Sharma, Arvind. "Reforming the Speaker's Role: A Comparative Study." *Commonwealth Parliamentary Review*, vol. 55, no. 2, 2020

³⁴ PRS Legislative Research. "Tracking MP Participation: Pilot Study." 2021

³⁵ Jain, Pranav. "Data-Driven Parliament: Can Metrics Improve Performance?" *LiveMint*, 2022

³⁶ Lok Sabha Secretariat. "Needs Assessment Survey for First-Term MPs." Internal Document, 2021

³⁷ IDSA. "Orientation and Capacity Building for Indian MPs." 2020

³⁸ NDTV. "MPs Want Predictable Parliamentary Calendar: Survey." June 2021

³⁹ Commonwealth Parliamentary Association. *Effective Scheduling and Calendar Practices in Legislatures*. London, 2019

MPs in constitution, which is sometimes abused for political gain. Many times, some statements can't be made in public by these MPs due to the fear of defamation charges. So members use their privilege and state the statements in the Parliament without any fear of repercussion. Though these defamatory and factually incorrect sentences are expunged from Parliament official record, but in age social media, such video clips of these statements creates nuisance and disruption in the country. Such statements must be dealt with more gravity than other indiscipline if any member makes a statement which is defamatory or factually incorrect in nature, then such member must either present proof of the statement within stipulated time or they must be punished with harsher punishment, like taking away their parliamentary privileges except residential and securities services, deducting their salary and putting financial liability.

IV. Ethics to be Followed

Many of the expected behaviour from MPs can be imposed or made to follow with punitive measures, but there are some behaviours which cannot be forced upon MPs rather they must follow these measures out of their will and duty towards the Constitution. In recent times, one of the most noticeable behaviour seen is the habit of walkouts by some MPs, which is commonly used in every session as tactic of gaining attention. No rules can be made regarding walkouts as it obstructs the rights of MPs to move freely, but when MPs walk out of the parliament, without hearing the other MPs, they go their duty to hear other MPs as the representative of their constituency and they obstruct healthy debates. So walkout as a practice should be discouraged and observed only in grave situations.

There are many punitive punishments, which are discussed in the above which provide lot of power to the speaker to maintain order in the Parliament, but currently there are still many power which speaker has to maintain order. Such powers are not used by the speaker due fear of political repercussion . This reluctance of speaker promotes unruly behaviour between MPs as they do not fear repercussion. Speaker can't be forced to punish MPs but they must understand their constitutional duty and maintain order in the parliament, using their power rather than fearing political repercussion .

As many members have financial and muscle power , they do not fear either financial repercussion or there privileges rescinded. These types of members must themselves follow the rules as "Laxman Rekha". Though they can't be forced to follow these rules, they can be suspended for their behaviour as with their suspension, other members can work properly.

V. Conclusion

The basic feature of any democratic country is its Parliament, so its smooth functioning is imperative for country to grow. For Parliament to function properly, proper rules of procedure needs to be there which not only govern the parliament, but also ensures its members follow the rules diligently. Recent chaos in houses have proven that these codes need change. The behaviour of MPs has showed that the punishment for not following the rules is not enough. There must be increase in punishment, which ensures that MPs are held liable for their behaviour and are severely punished with methods like salary deduction, rescinding privilege and financial liability. This punishments will not only make sure these MPs behave properly, but also send a message that creating a ruckus in the parliament will not be taken lightly.

Though punishment is not just enough, this must be dealt like carrot and stick approach where MPs who behave in orderly fashion must be appreciated by the house and the people, and those MPs, who behave in disorder fashion must be criticised by the people. For house to work properly, people must also take responsibility and not award those MPs who use parliament as a political tool rather than for public representation.

